

WORLD-LIFE BALANCE

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Abstract- Work-life balance is a very integral aspect of a professional's life. Work-life balance hugely affects the morale of a person which in turn can affect the productivity of a person in their field of work, and disruption of this balance can set off a domino effect. Work-life balance is not only important for a working professional in a corporate environment but it is equally important for a business owner to strike the perfect balance between their busy schedule and their leisure time. The main objective of this article is to present a comprehensive idea of work-life balance.[1]

Keywords-Work; Life; Time Management; Workplace; Leaves

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance can be roughly explained as the quantity of time someone spends on their professional endeavor as compared to the quantity of time the same person puts into performing activities not related to their profession. These activities include spending quality time with their family, practicing their favorite hobby, going on long drives, etc. Work-life balance has a direct effect on the efficiency of an individual and is a very vital aspect of any career. In modern times more emphasis is being put on Work-life balance as more and more professionals are considering their mental health and physical health that can be hampered by an unbalanced work life.

2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

2.1 To look how Work Life Balance affects employees' job satisfaction among workers in the UK's retail sector.

2.2 To assess the effects of Work Life Balance practices on both male and female employees.

2.3 To evaluate the impact of Work Life Balance on the wellbeing of employees in the retail sector.[2]

3.0 HISTORY OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Mainly, the first research in the field of Work-life balance was conducted in the 1960s. Many researchers studied Work-life balance as participation of women in different fields increased which meant that thousands of families could be observed as having both parents working jobs. The United States of America saw a very significant turn in Work-life balance much before when the erstwhile President signed the Fair Labor Standard Acts of 1938. This act ensured the setting of a minimum hourly wage, setting maximum work hours to 44 hours. Later the maximum hours one could work per week was further reduced to 40 hours. Work and family were historically seen as mutually exclusive but in 1977 Kanter highlighted the interconnectedness between work and family by putting the focus on the different effects of one's professional work on their family. Subsequently, many other theories came to the forefront, theories such as the Compensation theory devised by Staines in 1980, the Conflict theory devised by Greenhaus and Beuttle in 1985, and the Spillover theory gained much traction.^[3]

4.0 SOME POLICIES OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE MAY INCLUDE:

4.1 FLEXIBLE TIMING

Flexible timing can be further explained as non-static working hours, keeping in my mind the benefits to both the worker and employer. Flexible working hours refer to the system where employees can choose their leisure hours, the hours which they want to spend on themselves. This leads to a much more efficient workforce as employees get a perception of independence and rightfully so. It is quite visible that non-rigid working hours provide a very neat equilibrium between working hours and family time providing a great Work-life balance. The implementation of flexible timing has been prominent in the corporate world in the past decade.^[2]

4.2 FLEXIBLE WORKPLACE

A flexible workplace is another concept that has brewed up in the last decade but after the pandemic, the concept of working from home has exploded and it has proven to be a positive step. The "Work from Home" concept has saved companies significant money as there is no need to maintain office infrastructure. On the flip side of the coin, the employees also enjoy doing their work in the cozy environment of their homes. For working parents, this has been life-changing as they can take care of their children and also do their jobs to feed their tummies. This has definitely been a hugely positive step toward a Work-life balance.

4.3 INCREASED LEAVES

An appropriate number of leaves is very important for a good Work-life balance. It is important to get a much-deserved break after rigorous work hours. Nowadays various leaves are provided by organizations. Study leave, career leave, sick leave, and mourning leave are some of them. For mothers that are expecting their childbirth can avail of maternity leave. The availability of leaves builds great trust between an organization and its employees, proving that the organization cares about its employees.

5.0 HOW MANY COMPANIS PROMOTE WORK-LIFE BALANCE?

6.0 CONCLUSION

Work-life balance is a very important aspect of a professional's life in fact it might be considered the most vital aspect of a working professional's life. Much stress has been put on this topic by employers but there still exists some holes that must be filled to strike the perfect balance.

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